

SoildiverAgro project

Adoption of new management practices to increase crop production and quality

THE WHAT AND WHY

A changing climate causes challenges for farmers in the Central Atlantic Region

As the climate continues to evolve, farmers in the Central Atlantic Region are compelled to reassess traditional agricultural practices, particularly the rotation system. With shifting weather patterns, including altered precipitation levels and temperature fluctuations, farmers face unprecedented challenges in maintaining crop yields and soil health. A field experiment was organised during 2019 till 2023 in Flanders, Belgium, known for its temperate climate. It aimed at exploring to what extent new strategies (application of farm yard manure, whether or not co-composted with 'brow' material, and a differential management

of the cover crops (incorporation or mowing)) might maintain soil quality, sufficient crop yield and nitrogen supplying capacity. Unfortunately, the mean temperature in both 2020 and 2022 was the highest ever recorded since 1991. The number of tropical heat days and total precipitation was extremely high and low respectively. As a result, the potato yield in 2020 was low regardless of the different treatments (<35000 kg/ha while a yield of >40000 kg/ha in Flanders is normal), while the summer barley in 2022 with similar extreme weather conditions resulted in a normal yield of around 7 tons/ha or more.

HOW IS THE CHALLENGE ADDRESSED

Adaptations to the crop rotation system is desirable

Strategies such as diversifying crop varieties, adapting the rotation system avoiding water demanding crops, adjusting planting schedules, and implementing innovative irrigation

techniques are increasingly essential to mitigate the impacts of climate change on agricultural productivity.

1. Potato yield (2020) per treatment. (whiskers represent standard deviation). nAFV = cover crop destroyed and incorporated, AFV = cover crop mowed and removed, none = no organic fertilizer applied, FYM = farm yard manure added, FYMco = FYM co-composted with straw added (ILVO).

2. Summer barley (2022) yield per treatment. (whiskers represent standard deviation). nAFV = cover crop destroyed and incorporated, AFV = cover crop mowed and removed, none = no organic fertilizer applied, FYM = farm yard manure added, FYMco = FYM co-composted with straw added (ILVO).

KEYWORDS

Changing climate, rotation system, diversifying crop systems

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